

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Near Wake Evolution in Tidal Stream Turbine Wake Due to Asymmetric Inflow

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Abstract

Tidal stream turbines deployed at highly energetic open water sites are subjected to inflow asymmetry or shear flow in the rotor plane. The inflow shear is expected to affect the downstream wake and cause asymmetric loading on the rotor blades. Such effects are poorly understood for tidal turbines compared to wind turbines, where such asymmetric loading has been studied in detail. The asymmetric inflow problem for tidal turbines is expected to be different as the asymmetric loadings on the structure increase significantly due to the higher density of the fluid medium. In addition, the wake re-energization process is less prominent in tidal turbines due to the constrained vertical energy entrainment in tidal estuaries. In the present study, an active grid turbulence generator in the Tidal Turbine Testing Facility (T³F) at Lehigh University is used to seed in an inflow condition with elevated turbulence intensity coupled with flow shear to mimic real in-situ tidal flow conditions. A scaled tidal turbine model was used for testing, turbine performance measured in the sheared inflow conditions with an average Ti of 21% in the rotor plane is compared to the homogeneous inflow conditions with a turbulence intensity (Ti) of 2.2% (named quasi-laminar case). A drop of ~ 12% in the maximum power coefficients was observed for the sheared inflow conditions with lower power coefficients at high tip speed ratios observed compared to the no-shear cases. Particle Image Velocimeter (PIV) measurements were conducted in upper and lower half-planes to give insight into the near-wake evolution up to two diameters downstream.

Keywords: tidal stream turbine; shear inflow; PIV wake measurement.

1. Introduction

Tidal energy is a very promising renewable energy resource offering high energy density and ~98% predictability and is capable of generating 9% potential percent of US electricity generation [1]. Several studies have been undertaken to measure the tidal energy resource in several open water locations [2, 3, 4, 5]; the findings are summarized in Vinod & Banerjee [6]. The inflow characteristics at these locations include elevated levels of turbulence intensity, anisotropy in the flow, and flow shear in the water column. It is, therefore, important to characterize the tidal flow in detail for better estimation of turbine lifetime, maintenance cycle, and annual power generation.

Most laboratory studies of tidal stream turbines (TST) use a uniform inflow with low levels of inflow turbulence intensity. Nonetheless, the tidal flow in potential tidal energy sites is far more complex. While the flows in energetic tidal energy sites are typically characterized by shear velocity profiles, the studies of a tidal turbine under sheared

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inflow conditions are limited. Rahimain et al. [7] predicted the performance of two tidal turbines with BEM (Blade Element Momentum) in shear flow and validated the results with experiments performed in a towing tank. The results showed that the shear velocity profile does not significantly affect the mean performance, but it imparts a cyclic effect to the transient loadings. Using a wall-mounted obstacle, Gaurier et al. [8] investigated the effect of shear on the blade root force and observed a force variation of $\sim 20\%$ of its time average value during a rotational cycle. Vinod et al. [9] studied the near-wake characteristics of a 1:20-scaled TST model. A drop ranging from 5% to 15% in performance was observed in sheared inflow conditions. They also observed a prominent asymmetry in wake profiles in terms of velocity deficits, turbulence intensities, and integral length scales. All these studies are valuable in helping the development and deployment of tidal turbines.

Following the work presented by Vinod et al. [9], this paper focused on the detailed wake characterization and wake re-energization process in a sheared, turbulent inflow condition. The mean velocity profile generated in the present study has a smooth mean velocity variation in the vertical direction and was highly turbulent. With Particle Image Velocimeter (PIV), special attention has been paid to exploring the effect of the wake asymmetric on the wake recovery process in the upper and lower region. The wake re-energization process was quantified based on momentum and kinetic energy flux.

2. Methodology

In the present study, Makita-type active grid turbulence generator [10] in the Tidal Turbine Testing Facility (T³F) at Lehigh University is used to seed in an inflow condition with elevated turbulence intensity coupled with flow shear. As shown in Fig. 1a, a total number of ten shafts (five horizontally and five vertically) are used to help perturb the inflow. All horizontally attached winglets are solid, and all vertically attached winglets are hollow to avoid a high blockage ratio. In the present study, a DRP (double random protocol - direction of rotation and angular velocity are randomized) [6] was adopted for the five vertical shafts, while the horizontal shafts are locked at present angles (see Fig. 1b) to generate a sheared velocity profile. A similar technique was used by Vinod et al. [9]; however, those experiments did not include the vertical shafts and were run in a static grid mode. The current experiments use a protocol where the vertical shafts are rotated at speeds of 1 Hz to create a dynamic shear that increases turbulent mixing and produces smoother velocity and turbulence kinetic energy profiles. As shown in Fig. 1b, the turbine model tested is a 1:20 scaled, three-bladed horizontal axis tidal turbine. The rotor area is 0.061 m^2 with a diameter of 0.2794 m , resulting in a blockage ratio of 16% when divided by the cross-section area of the water tunnel. All blades have the same section profile of SG6043, and a constant chord length, c , of 0.016 m .

Fig. 1. Schematic of (a) ten-shaft active grid; (b) 1:20 scale tidal turbine model and PIV field of view up to 2D downstream.

A detailed flow field measurement was carried out using a high-resolution, two-dimensional stereo-PIV system (TSI Inc). The required illumination was provided by an ND: YAG (Neodymium-doped Yttrium Aluminum Garnet) laser system with an average output of 100 mJ per Pulse. The laser sheet is parallel to the XY plane and has an offset of 0.057 m ($Z = 0.2 D$) away from the center plane to avoid the nacelle. In the present study, the cameras are set to capture a field of view (FOV) of $0.3 \text{ m} \times 0.3 \text{ m}$ with a sampling frequency of 72 Hz. As shown in Fig. 1b, four planes with a total axial distance of up to 2D are measured to illustrate the upper and lower wake region for the shear case. The overlap between two adjacent FOVs is 0.04 m and 0.092 m in axial and vertical directions, respectively.

3. Results

3.1. Inflow calibration and performance characteristics

The inflow velocity profile was measured by a Nortek Vectrino+ Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter (ADV) at the rotor plane location ($X=0.5D$) in the absence of the turbine model. In the present study, the measurements were done at the center plane ($Z=0$) with a sampling frequency 50Hz, consistent with our previous study[6]. Fig. 2a presents the streamwise mean velocities and the turbulence intensities as a function of height, y . A power-law equation was used to fit the velocity profile, given as:

$$U(y) = U_{hub} \left(\frac{y}{y_{hub}} \right)^n \quad (1)$$

The symbol, n , denotes the shear exponent for the velocity profile and was estimated to be 0.455 for the studied case, corresponding to a high shear flow condition measured for ebb tides as reported by Colby and Corren[11]. The power-law curve fitting has an R^2 value of 0.87, within an acceptable range. A more significant variation in turbulence intensity was shown in Fig. 2a. The turbulence intensity ranges from ~12% to ~30% across all the water column depth, and the averaged turbulence intensity was estimated to be 21% within the rotor area, similar to that in a high-energy tidal site.

Fig. 2. (a) Inflow velocity and turbulence intensity profiles; (b) Effect of flow conditions on power coefficients and standard deviations.

The power coefficients and the standard deviations for the dynamic shear inflow conditions are plotted and compared with the Quasi-Laminar case ($Ti \sim 2.2\%$; homogeneous inflow without shear and turbulence). As shown in Fig. 2b, the maximum C_p for the shear case is ~12% lower than the quasi-laminar case. Nevertheless, the mean power and coefficients were barely affected at $TSR < 3$. The standard deviations of the power coefficients are also given in Fig. 2b. For $TSR < 3$, the standard deviation between the two cases is negligible. However, the larger the TSR, the greater the impact of the turbulence level of the inflow conditions.

3.2. Mean flow

The normalized mean streamwise velocity contour ($U^* = U/U_\infty$) plots of the measured FOVs under quasi-laminar and sheared inflow are presented in Fig. 3. All the PIV results shown here were conducted at the optimal TSR, ~4.6. The velocity values shown are normalized by the freestream velocity, $U_\infty = 0.82m/s$. Similar to the quasi-laminar case, significant velocity reduction was observed in the near wake region. Nevertheless, the significant difference under the sheared inflow was the fast convection of the slow-moving wake in the upper half region compared to the lower half region. The faster velocities seem to push the wake downwards due to the momentum deficit between the upper and lower planes and subsequently tilt the inner wake clockwise. Furthermore, the wake expansion in the upper half is more noticeable than that in the lower half region, while in the lower half region, the effect of the flow acceleration in the bypass region diminished significantly due to the slow inflow velocities. Following the work by Kolekar et al.[12], the near-wake region is divided into five regions in the quasi-laminar case. As shown in Fig. 4a, a low-velocity zone (Region I) was observed close to the blade root, which is formed due to the blockage of the blade root. Two cone-like regions (Region II and III located above and below the centerline) are formed behind the blade rotational area, with the low velocity preserved until $X/R=4.0$. A local accelerated velocity zone (Region IV) was also

observed due to the lower blockage of the local blade section area close to the root. A new region V was observed due to the existence of the turbine nacelle body, which decelerated the flow while intensifying the turbulence kinetic energy (see next section). For the shear case, the regions defined in the near wake are significantly altered as the wake is highly stratified. In the upper half plane, a high-velocity zone (Region IV) was observed. This region has a velocity comparable to the inflow velocity and is completely absent in the lower half plane. In contrast, regions II, III, and V encompass both the upper and lower half-plane. A slow-moving wake region II(a) was developed right behind region IV in the upper half plane while, in the lower half plane, region II(b) originated from the blade location. Compared to Region II, Region III was intensively deformed due to the higher inflow velocity in the upper half region. Close to the nacelle body, region V was observed, with the low-velocity areas larger than those in the quasi-laminar case.

Fig. 3. Mean streamwise velocity contour plots under (a) quasi-laminar inflow; (b) sheared inflow on four PIV planes.

3.3. Turbulent Kinetic Energy

The contour plots of the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE), normalized by the square of the freestream velocity U_∞^2 , are shown in Fig. 4. Compared to the quasi-laminar case, where the TKE is mainly concentrated in the shear layer region (Region II and III), the TKE for the shear case is spread across the entire near-wake region. At locations close to $X/R = 0$ (close to the rotor plane), the TKE values are significantly larger in the shear case than their counterpart in the quasi-laminar case due to the high turbulence intensity in the shear inflow. In Fig. 4a, a region of high TKE (Region I) was observed at locations close to the nacelle body. Interestingly, the wake core (Region V) in both cases has the largest TKE values. It indicates that while the presence of the nacelle body slows the mean velocity, it intensifies the TKE; at all measured planes, the TKE values are higher in the shear case than those in the quasi-laminar case.

Fig. 4. Contour plots of turbulence kinetic energy for (a) shear inflow; (b) quasi-laminar inflow.

3.4. Reynolds stresses and Momentum flux

The contour plot of the Reynolds shear stresses $-\overline{u'v'}$, normalized by the square of the freestream velocity, U_∞^2 , are given in Fig. 5a and 5c. Based on RANS (Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes) equations (the vertical turbulent transport term), positive values in the upper half region represent a momentum flux downwards, while negative values in the lower half region represent an upward momentum flux. To better quantify the evolution of momentum flux in the depthwise direction, the Reynolds shear stresses $-\overline{u'v'}$, was integrated as follows[13]:

$$MF = \frac{1}{AU_{\infty}^2} \int_A -\overline{u'v'} dx dy \quad (2)$$

where A is the area of each integral section, MF is the momentum flux within the section. The streamwise extension of each integral section was set to be $0.5R$ (~ 0.07 m). As observed in Fig. 5b, the momentum flux (MF) in equation (2) in the upper shear layer region is larger than its counterpart in the lower plane. However, for $X/R > 3.5$, the value of the momentum flux drops to negative in the upper half region while its value turns positive in the lower half region. This abrupt change is attributed to the tip vortex instability [13]. At $X/R \sim 3.5$, a leapfrogging instability breaks the periodic behavior of the tip vortices, resulting in a rapid drop in the momentum/kinetic energy flux. Furthermore, at locations close to the rotor plane ($X/R < 0.5$), the momentum flux was small for both quasi-Laminar and shear cases. However, for the shear case, the momentum flux in the lower and upper half regions gradually increases without abrupt changes. At $X/R \sim 4.0$, the total momentum flux entrained into the wake in the upper shear region reaches almost three times larger than that in the lower shear layer region for the shear case.

Fig. 5. Contour of Reynolds shear stresses, $-\overline{u'v'}$ for (a) the quasi-laminar inflow, and (c) and the shear inflow; histogram of the momentum flux for (b) the quasi-laminar inflow, and (d) and the shear inflow.

4. Conclusion

An experimental study on the shear effect in the wake of a tidal turbine model has been performed using the stereo-PIV method. The study reveals the significant effect of the shear velocity profile on the evolution of the near wake region. An intense wake expansion was observed in the upper shear layer. The momentum flux was also found to be more pronounced in the upper half region of the wake; an almost threefold increase in the absolute magnitude of momentum flux is observed compared to the lower half plane for the shear layer. The turbulent kinetic energy was also preserved longer at $Y/R=1.0$, with the nacelle body substantially amplifying the turbulence kinetic energy.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to acknowledge the US National Science Foundation (Grant No. 1706358, CBET- Fluid Dynamics) for the financial support that has facilitated the research in this publication.

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